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Factors in the formation of
spiritual morality in young people.

Annotation: *The purpose of writing this article is to discuss together the essence and goals of spiritual and moral education of young people, the main aspects of moral education.*

Keywords: *Parental responsibility, morality, literature, spirituality, social environment, values.*

Parents do not spare anything from their child. This is the greatness that nature has given them. It is a child's duty to respect their parents, to be in their service, to receive their blessings. Today, some members of the younger generation are accused of immorality, insecurity and aggression. Therefore we must explain to them the process of formation of "Spiritual-moral education" in his mind the process of this moral feelings, moral position, moral behavior. The idea of spiritual and moral development of man in the basis for the up bringing of the modern person. Spiritual and moral up bringing creates conditions for the up bringing of a person who lives in accordance with his conscience. Literature enriches a person spiritually, shapes the spiritual and moral qualities of a person. In the story "The Reader" by the famous Russian writers M. GORKY, a brief description of the essence of literature words like get, wake up.

The most important task facing all teachers today is to inculcate in the minds of young people the ideas of the ideology of national independence.

Both theoretically and practically to solve problems correctly on the basis of national values. Bringing up the younger generation is a very delicate art and it should be taken very seriously all of this should become a value of will educate new generations. Uzbek traditions, ceremonies and holidays are colourful and unique, formed over thousand of years. This values various events and situations emerging activities patterns. Spiritually, values and national ideology are very complex and multifaceted spheres of society both in the development of humanity as a whole. The nation and the national idea are most relevant and decisive factor. Today's youth must have a deep understanding of the forms and specific meaning of our national traditions. Only then will the next generation become people who will preserve the values, spirituality and culture of Uzbek nation, and protect the homeland. It is important of parents and educators work together to achieve these noble goals. The verses will not go unnoticed by the next generation.

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